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Research Article

**THE EFFECTIVENESS OF MENTORING PROGRAM FOR
MEDICAL STUDENTS REGARDING STUDENT'S
PERCEPTION, LANGUAGE AND ETHNICITY**¹Dr. Iqra Irshad, ²Noman Tariq Khan, ³Dr. Mahmood Ali Raza¹Women Medical Officer, Tehsil Headquater Muridke²Medical Officer, Cardiac Centre Chunian³Medical Officer, Rural Health Center Mamunkanjan**Abstract:**

Objective: The exploration of the mentoring program in a Medical College, on a subset of medical students.

Method: Our research participants included three hundred MBBS students first, second, and third year (Group B, C, and D respectively) which was carried out at Allied Hospital, Faisalabad (March 2016 to February 2017). A Likert Scale questionnaire was presented, which was filled by 256 students. Positively mannered statements were included in the questionnaire so that the agreement of the students provides the maximum level of satisfaction with a good mentoring program. To receive a clearer concept of the students, open-ended questions were also included. Our study used both quantitative and qualitative methods of research.

Results: The research outcome shows a higher level of satisfaction of students being mentored among group B, and C comparing group D (p-value of 0.001). The comparison between all three groups was checked by Tukey's test application. The outcome shows that the majority of the students were in favour of mentoring for both academic and non-academic lives. The students of all three groups also made reports that the mentor is most of the time ready and available for the resolution of internal conflicts. Most of the students confirmed the record kept by a mentor but email communication was reported to be limited.

Conclusion: Mentoring allows many students to carry on a smooth routine, both non-academic and academic. The students agreed with the fact that their studies were continued due to the help and guidance of a mentor and they appreciated their presence as well.

Keywords: Mentor, Mentee, Mentoring, Multicultural, Medical students.

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INTRODUCTION:

The concept of a mentor is as old as Greek mythology. Odysseus's wife Penelope gave birth to a child Telemachus. Due to the non-availability of his father, he was entrusted to Athena (goddess of wisdom) by her mother. Athena's mentoring brought up Telemachus to be a young successful man [1, 2]. Mentoring is a communication between a mentor and mentee in a peaceful environment for the guidance of a mentee. Ideally, the mentor should be of high rank and old age than mentee [3, 4]. In the USA, medical students' mentoring started in 1990 and it is still [4] in progress. This strategy is receiving a lot of attention in Pakistan as well. Pakistan has many provinces with diverse cultures and different languages [5] and language variations. In Pakistan, a student enters a medical college after completing twelve or thirteen years of schooling. The average age of these students entering on merit [6] to professional colleges is 18 ± 1 year. Being from different cultural backgrounds, students face many adjustment issues. Therefore, the mentoring program began right with the inception of this college [7, 8]. To deal with this situation, our mentors work on psychological domain too, for which they received regular workshops. Each mentor is assigned ten mentees until those mentees pass out after five years [9]. With all the hurdles, medical students continue to improve slowly and steadily through the guidance of a mentoring program and mentors identify his/her mentee's weaknesses and strengths. Sensitive mentees shy and try to hide their issues. This condition may become so problematic that literature research reports many strenuous studies of medicine lead to committing suicide [10]. Mentors take several sessions of mentoring to identify students' difficulties. The students with difficulties are counselled and they are mentioned for a mentoring program to their supervisors [11]. Mentees feel free to share everything with their mentor because just venting out their issues help them too. Several studies show that mentoring helps both mentees and mentors [11, 12]. With the increase in a number of suicide cases among medical students, concerns are raised to make mentoring more essential so that mentors can work more honestly and effectively. Although, not all

non-academic issues of mentees are solved but the listening capabilities of mentors, help the students to improve from unconfident student to a confident and smart doctor, ready to enter his/her profession with skills, sound knowledge and good attitude [12]. The exploration of mentoring program in a Medical College, on a subset of medical students in Pakistan.

METHODS

Our research participants included three hundred MBBS students first, second, and third year (Group B, C, and D respectively) which was carried out at Allied Hospital, Faisalabad (March 2016 to February 2017). The questionnaire was self-reported anonymously, filled by 256 students and collected by the stall. Likert scale questionnaire included options of strongly disagree, disagree, neutral, agree, and strongly agree as 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 respectively. Positively mannered statements were included in the questionnaire so that the agreement of the students provides maximum level of satisfaction with a good mentoring program. To receive a clearer concept of the students, open-ended questions were also included. Our study used both quantitative and qualitative methods of research.

SPSS was used for data analysis, Chi-square was used for assessing total variables and Tukey's test was used for analysing individual statements. "P value of equal to or less than 0.05 was considered significant.

RESULTS

The research outcome shows a higher level of satisfaction of students being mentored among group B, and C comparing group D. Chi-square shows p-value of 0.001. The comparison between all three groups was checked by Tukey's test application. The students of all three groups also made reports that the mentor is most of the time ready and available for the resolution of internal conflicts. Most of the students confirmed the record kept by a mentor but email communication was reported to be limited. Different language groups with their frequency. The themes selected for open-ended questions were trust, privacy, confidentiality, responsibility, and personality. Grouping of the questions was done in accordance with the themes and answers received accumulatively were:

Table – I: Questions and Responses

Question	Responses
Q 1. Do you put your trust in your mentor regarding all your academic and non-academic issues?	“I usually don’t have any issues but I trust my mentor talking to him” “I share my academic issues mostly” “I feel satisfied sharing my non-academic issues with my mentor but I wish she had more power to solve them”
Q 2. Do you find any issues regarding privacy or confidentiality?	“I feel total privacy attending the mentoring session in a separate room” “I express my thoughts openly”
Q 3. What is your reaction to an unsolved problem after your mentoring sessions?	“I get irritated to the problems which my mentor is unable to solve” “I feel calm because everyone has a limitation”
Q 4. What development do you find in your personality after mentoring sessions?	“I have become confident” “My dressing selection has been improved” “I feel no change in my personality”
Q 5. What is the importance of mentoring in your life?	“It helps me express” “It helped me in becoming a confident individual” “Mentoring helped me in becoming a better student” “It is good to know someone is there to hear you always”

Table – II: Mentoring and the level of well-being and satisfaction

Group	SA		A		N		DA		SDA		Total Responses	p-value
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%		
B (85)	167	39.29	140	32.94	80	18.82	28	6.5	10	2.3	425	0.001
C (109)	344	63.11	153	28.07	22	4.03	20	3.66	6	1.1	545	
D (62)	33	10.64	130	41.93	120	38.7	14	14	13	4.19	310	
Total	544	42.05	423	33.04	222	17.34	62	4.84	29	2.26	1280	

Table – III: The graph of Students’ perception

Statement	1st Year	2nd Year	3rd Year
Satisfactory	88	87	90
Scheduled Displaced	99	95	95
Privacy	82	75	65
Confidentiality	79	64	76
Separate Rooms	40	30	20
Portfolio	97	95	97
Helped in Achievement	86	80	70
Trained Mentors	73	86	98
Personal Development	82	87	90
Brought Discipline	62	77	83
Interaction with Peers	80	83	87
Voice Grievances	90	97	90
Counseling	93	96	92
Relaxed	93	97	98
Share Problems	83	87	90
Academic Resolution	62	77	70
Communication	97	98	97
Trustful Relationship	97	97	100
Feedback	75	76	74
Share Success	89	87	98

Table – IV: Frequency of Mother tongue and Ethnicity

Language	Percentage
Urdu	37.89
Punjabi	1.95
Pushto	13.28
Baluchi	39.06
Urdu	7.81

DISCUSSION:

Mentoring is an essential need of all students starting their career in medicine [13] as it plays a vital role in flourishing their personalities for a better academic medicine career [14]. It has been reported that

mentorship prevails its advantages for both individual and organization [15]. However, not all medical colleges in Pakistan has started a mentoring program. A research conducted in 2010 by Usmani *et al.* [16] found that a mentorship program at this college

brought significant changes in mentees with high satisfaction among mentors for carrying this noble task. It is suggested that the mentor and mentee's faculty [17] should keep mentoring programs under evaluation. The criteria of mentorship state that mentoring program should include all the students as stated by Meinal [18]. The mentorship limit is minimum of 01 years with no limit for maximum time. The program is for the overall improvement of mentees. There are seven themes, which were the basis for the development of the questionnaire. Mentors establish an environment, which helps the mentees in realizing their potential of becoming a successful professional individual [19]. The utmost importance for mentors is to keep a keen focus on the professional growth of mentees [20]. A research of Borch *et al.* reports that mentees depend on mentors for providing them guidance and counselling in becoming true professionals and achieving their goal [20]. Mentees provided the fact that mentors have helped them in achieving academic progress, psychological improvement and emotional stability. This is indeed, stated as a very significant quality of a mentor-mentee relationship [21]. As our study reveals that those medical students came from different backgrounds, they felt shyness but mentoring programs provided them with social interactions through meetings in groups and individual and helped them become extroverts. Mentors helped and supported them in the achievement of improving communication skills, interpersonal dealings, learning habits, positive attitude, and problem-solving strategies [22]. A research by Straus *et al.* states that mentoring can be made effective through dedication, and continual meetings among mentees and mentors [23]. Our research found that mentees hold the opinion that their mentors give provide them with help whenever they are needed. Mentees feel very secure in sharing their issues because of the trust and confidentiality the mentors provide them [23]. A large number of students find their mentors trustworthy. This program befits both the organization and the individual. A mentor provides mentees with guidance, answering questions and giving valuable suggestions [24]. Our research proves that mentors have achieved this task evidently. They have the quality of providing great professional advice as well as excellent counselling. Expressing their problems more freely empowers the mentees to make their own decisions more confidently [24]. A mentor is an important element in keeping the well-being of his/her mentee, states Reman *et al.* research [22]. The support of mentor-mentee relationship shows the effectiveness of a mentoring program [14]. Mentors provide the

learning of values, ethics, professionalism, and emotional support, which cannot be learnt from textbooks. It benefits both mentor and mentee as mentors improve their efficiency and receive career satisfaction and mentees build an explicit, mutually respected communication relationship with their mentors [18, 23]. Medical students deal with a heavy workload and mentors help them achieve balance in their lives, therefore, Usmani A. reports the importance of the role of a mentor in achieving students' goals [24].

CONCLUSION:

In a setting of multi-cultural medical students who undergo strenuous studies for five years, a constant mentoring program proves very successful. The presence of mentors provides a stress-free environment to the medical students in continuing their academic and non-academic routine. Medical students approve the presence of mentors in their time of conflicts.

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